

Supplementary Information: Ferroelectric Control of Interlayer Excitons in 3R-MoS₂ / MoSe₂ Heterostructures

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CONTENTS

I. Methods	2
A. Heterostructure fabrication	2
B. Continuous-wave μ -PL mapping measurements	2
C. Time-resolved μ -PL measurements	2
D. μ -PL excitation measurements	2
E. Second harmonic generation measurements	3
F. Computational Details	3
II. Details on Numerical Calculations	3
III. Additional Computational Results	5
IV. Observation of domain dependent ILX PL and domain wall motion in an additional sample	8
V. AFM measurements	10
VI. Redshift of the ILX in different heterostructures	11
VII. Second Harmonic Generation	13
References	13

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I. METHODS

A. Heterostructure fabrication

Thin Au/Ti (16/3 nm) electrodes were realized by a maskless photolithography system (Smartprint) and metal evaporation onto silicon substrates covered by 300 nm of SiO₂. The heterostructure was then fabricated using a polycarbonate (PC)/polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) - assisted heated transfer of few-layer of hBN and 3R-MoS₂ and monolayers of MoSe₂ (HQGraphene). Flakes were first exfoliated and then optically selected (by comparing their contrast to flakes of known thickness) on SiO₂ (hBN) or on PDMS(MoS₂/MoSe₂). The few-layers MoS₂ and monolayers of MoSe₂ were then aligned to each other and stamped onto one PDMS film. A PC/PDMS stack was then prepared and used as transfer agent with the van der Waals pick up method [1, 2]. The heterostack was carefully aligned with the already picked up hBN on a PC/PDMS glass slide and lastly dropped on the electrodes of the silicon substrate. The completed stack was then washed in chloroform for 1 h and subsequently thermally annealed in forming gas at 180 °C for 3 hours.

B. Continuous-wave μ -PL mapping measurements

For the PL mapping measurements two different setups were used:

Setup 1 (University of Rostock): The samples were excited with a 2.33 eV continuous-wave diode laser focused to a spot size of about 1.5 μ m using a 50x microscope objective. The samples were mounted in a helium-flow cryostat (CryoVac Konti Micro) and cooled to a temperature of 4 K. The PL light emitted by the sample is collected using the same objective, filtered by long-pass filters and analyzed with a combination of a spectrometer (Princeton Acton SP2300), a charged-coupled device (CCD) and an InGaAs photodiode array (Princeton PyLoN-IR). The InGaAs photodiode array was cooled by liquid nitrogen to 200 K during all experiments. To obtain PL maps of the samples, the cryostat, with the samples inside, was moved in relation to the fixed laser spot through a computer-controlled xy stage. For the gating experiments, the samples were contacted using a gold-wire bonder on a custom copper PCB, which was connected to pins inside the cryostat. By using a Fischer connector and a break-out-box the connections were transmitted to a Keithley 2450 Sourcemeter, which was controlled remotely by a computer.

Setup 2 (TU Munich): For μ -PL maps a single-frequency 633 nm laser diode was used for the excitation. Low laser powers of about 2 μ W focused through a microscope objective with high numerical aperture (NA = 0.82) were employed. xy scanners (by Attocube) were employed to move the sample during the map. The luminescence signal was collected in a backscattering configuration and was spectrally dispersed by a 0.5 m focal length monochromator (HRS500 by Princeton Instruments) equipped with a 300 grooves/mm grating (with blaze at 1 μ m). The signal was then detected by an etalon-free electrically-cooled Si CCD camera (Blaze 100HRX by Princeton Instruments). The laser light was filtered out by a long-pass filter at 650 nm. The sample temperature was about 7 K during the measurement.

C. Time-resolved μ -PL measurements

For time-resolved μ -PL measurements, the sample was excited with a ps supercontinuum laser (NKT Photonics) tuned at about 530 nm, with a full width at half maximum of about 8 nm and 50 ps pulses at 1.2 MHz repetition rate. A high NA (0.75) objective was employed to focus the laser beam (with 0.5 μ W laser power) and collect the signal in a backscattering configuration. The desired spectral region corresponding to the interlayer exciton emission was selected through longpass and shortpass filters, and the signal was collected through an avalanche photodetector from MPD with temporal resolution of 30 ps. The sample temperature was about 6 K during the measurement.

D. μ -PL excitation measurements

For μ -PL excitation (μ -PLE), the same ps supercontinuum laser (with 77.8 MHz repetition rate) and objective used for time-resolved μ -PL were employed. The laser wavelength was changed by an acousto-optic tunable filter, resulting in a bandwidth of about 8 nm. Shortpass and longpass filters were used when appropriate to remove spurious signals from the laser. A laser power of 40 μ W was employed. The luminescence signal was collected in a backscattering configuration, through a 0.2 m focal length monochromator (by Princeton Instruments) equipped with a 300 grooves/mm grating (with blaze at 1 μ m), and an etalon-free N₂-cooled Si CCD camera (100BRX by Princeton

Instruments). The laser light was filtered out by long-pass filters. The sample temperature was about 6 K during the measurement.

E. Second harmonic generation measurements

The measurements were performed by using a tunable pulsed Ti:Sapphire laser at 925 nm, with a pulse width of < 100 fs and a repetition rate of 80 MHz. The sample was excited and measured with a high NA objective (0.9), and the frequency-doubled light was collected in a backscattering configuration. A linear polarizer was used to select the experimental configuration with co-polarized laser and SHG signal. A half waveplate mounted on motorized rotation stage was used for polarization-resolved measurements. The signal was collected through a 0.2 m focal length monochromator (by Princeton Instruments) equipped with a 300 grooves/mm grating (with blaze at $1 \mu\text{m}$), and a etalon-free N_2 -cooled Si CCD camera (100BRX by Princeton Instruments). The sample was kept at room temperature during the measurement.

F. Computational Details

Density functional theory (DFT) calculations with the projector augmented-wave (PAW) method [3, 4] were performed using the Vienna Ab initio Simulation Package (VASP) [5, 6]. Exchange–correlation effects were treated using the Perdew–Burke–Ernzerhof (PBE) functional within the generalized gradient approximation (GGA), including van der Waals interactions via the D3 dispersion correction by Grimme (PBE+D3) [7, 8]. PBE was used for structural relaxations and ground-state electronic structure calculations. To improve the accuracy of band gaps, hybrid functional calculations were also performed using the Heyd–Scuseria–Ernzerhof functional (HSE06). A plane-wave energy cutoff of 450 eV was used for all calculations. The Brillouin zone was sampled using a Γ -centered Monkhorst–Pack mesh of $12 \times 12 \times 1$ \mathbf{k} -points. A vacuum spacing greater than 20 Å was included along the out-of-plane direction to prevent spurious interlayer interactions.

To construct the heterostructure models, we first optimized the in-plane lattice constants of the individual monolayers, obtaining 3.166 Å for MoS_2 and 3.295 Å for MoSe_2 , corresponding to a lattice mismatch of approximately 4.1%. To minimize strain and ensure periodic boundary conditions, we imposed a common in-plane lattice constant equal to the arithmetic mean of the two values, resulting in $a = 3.231$ Å. This leads to a symmetric biaxial strain of about +2.1% in MoS_2 and –1.9% in MoSe_2 . All atomic positions were relaxed while keeping the in-plane lattice fixed. To assess alternative modeling strategies, we also tested several commensurate supercell combinations, including 4×4 MoS_2 / 3×3 MoSe_2 , 5×5 / 4×4 , 7×7 / 6×6 , and 9×9 / 8×8 configurations. In all cases, the residual mismatch between the two layers remained greater than 7%, even for relatively large supercells, rendering them computationally expensive and unsuitable for systematic exploration of stacking-dependent effects. Moreover, the introduction of large supercells would complicate the analysis by folding the Brillouin zone and obscuring direct comparison across configurations. Therefore, we adopted the primitive unit cell with an averaged lattice parameter as a computationally efficient and physically justified approximation.

Ferroelectric polarization was computed using the Berry phase formalism [9–11], employing a dense $16 \times 16 \times 1$ \mathbf{k} -point mesh.

Many-body perturbation theory was employed to calculate the quasiparticle and optical excitation properties of the systems. Quasiparticle energies were obtained using partially self-consistent GW_0 (E VGW_0) calculations based on the PBE functional. In this scheme, the eigenvalues in the Green’s function G were iterated to convergence while the orbitals and the screened Coulomb interaction W_0 remained fixed at the DFT level, following the procedure of Hybertsen and Louie [12].

Optical absorption spectra were calculated by solving the Bethe–Salpeter equation (BSE), which accounts for correlated electron–hole excitations [13, 14]. For the GW and BSE calculations, we employed PAW pseudopotentials specifically optimized for many-body perturbation theory (GW PAW potentials), which include additional semicore states in the valence configuration. All E VGW_0 and BSE calculations were performed using a Γ -centered $12 \times 12 \times 1$ \mathbf{k} -point grid. The number of unoccupied bands was set to 32 for bilayer MoS_2 and $\text{MoS}_2/\text{MoSe}_2$, and increased to 64 for the 2L- $\text{MoS}_2/\text{MoSe}_2$ systems.

II. DETAILS ON NUMERICAL CALCULATIONS

The projector augmented-wave (PAW) method [3, 4] was employed to describe the interactions between core and valence electrons, with valence configurations of Mo ($4s^2 4p^6 4d^5 5s^1$), S ($3s^2 3p^4$), and Se ($4s^2 4p^4$). The corresponding

atomic radii are approximately 190, 88, and 103 pm, respectively [15].

All atomic positions were relaxed until the residual forces were below $0.01 \text{ eV } \text{\AA}^{-1}$ and the total energy was converged to within 10^{-8} eV .

Ferroelectric polarization was computed using the theory of polarization within the Berry phase formalism [9–11], employing a dense $16 \times 16 \times 1$ \mathbf{k} -point mesh. The macroscopic polarization \mathbf{P} was evaluated as:

$$\mathbf{P} = -\frac{e}{(2\pi)^3} \sum_n \int_{\text{BZ}} d\mathbf{k} \langle u_{n\mathbf{k}} | \nabla_{\mathbf{k}} | u_{n\mathbf{k}} \rangle, \quad (1)$$

where e is the elementary charge, $u_{n\mathbf{k}}$ is the periodic part of the Bloch function for the n th occupied band, and the integral is performed over the Brillouin zone (BZ).

The Berry curvature $\Omega_z(\mathbf{k})$ was evaluated using the Kubo-like formula:

$$\Omega_z(\mathbf{k}) = -\sum_n f_n \sum_{n' \neq n} \frac{2 \text{Im} [\langle \psi_{n\mathbf{k}} | v_x | \psi_{n'\mathbf{k}} \rangle \langle \psi_{n'\mathbf{k}} | v_y | \psi_{n\mathbf{k}} \rangle]}{(E_{n'} - E_n)^2}, \quad (2)$$

where v_x and v_y are the velocity operators in the x and y directions, f_n is the Fermi–Dirac occupation factor, and E_n are the Kohn–Sham eigenvalues.

Many-body perturbation theory was used to compute quasiparticle and optical excitation properties. In this work, quasiparticle energies were obtained using partially self-consistent GW_0 (EVGW₀) calculations, where the eigenvalues in the Green’s function G are iterated while keeping the orbitals and the screened Coulomb interaction W_0 fixed [16, 17].

Optical absorption spectra were calculated by solving the Bethe–Salpeter equation (BSE), which accounts for correlated electron–hole excitations [13, 14]. For the GW and BSE calculations, we employed PAW pseudopotentials specifically optimized for many-body perturbation theory (GW PAW potentials), which include additional semicore states in the valence configuration. All EVGW₀ and BSE calculations were performed using a Γ -centered $12 \times 12 \times 1$ \mathbf{k} -point grid. The number of unoccupied bands was set to 32 for bilayer MoS₂ and MoS₂/MoSe₂, and increased to 64 for the 2L-MoS₂/MoSe₂ systems.

The quasiparticle equation reads [16, 17]:

$$\varepsilon_i^{\text{QP}} = \varepsilon_i^{\text{KS}} + \langle \phi_i^{\text{KS}} | \Sigma(\varepsilon_i^{\text{QP}}) - V_{\text{XC}} | \phi_i^{\text{KS}} \rangle, \quad (3)$$

where $\varepsilon_i^{\text{KS}}$ and ϕ_i^{KS} are the Kohn–Sham eigenvalues and wave functions, Σ is the nonlocal self-energy operator, and V_{XC} is the exchange–correlation potential from the underlying density-functional calculation.

Optical absorption spectra were computed by solving the Bethe–Salpeter equation (BSE), which describes correlated electron–hole excitations [13, 14]. The effective two-particle Hamiltonian is:

$$H^{\text{BSE}} = H_{\text{diag}} + H_{\text{dir}} + 2H_x, \quad (4)$$

where H_{diag} contains independent quasiparticle transitions, H_{dir} represents the screened Coulomb attraction between the excited electron and the hole (excitonic effects), and H_x is the bare exchange interaction. The factor of two accounts for spin degeneracy in non-spin-polarized systems. The BSE eigenvalues E^λ are the excitation energies, and the amplitudes $A_{v\mathbf{c}\mathbf{k}}^\lambda$ give the weight of each valence-to-conduction ($v \rightarrow c$) transition at momentum \mathbf{k} .

The oscillator amplitude for excitation λ is given by:

$$t_\lambda = \sum_{v\mathbf{c}\mathbf{k}} A_{v\mathbf{c}\mathbf{k}}^\lambda \frac{\langle v\mathbf{k} | \hat{\mathbf{p}} | c\mathbf{k} \rangle}{\varepsilon_{c\mathbf{k}} - \varepsilon_{v\mathbf{k}}}, \quad (5)$$

which determines the macroscopic optical response through the imaginary part of the dielectric function:

$$\text{Im } \varepsilon_M(\omega) = \frac{8\pi^2}{\Omega} \sum_\lambda |t_\lambda|^2 \delta(\omega - E^\lambda), \quad (6)$$

where Ω is the unit cell volume.

To suppress spurious Coulomb coupling between periodic images along the non-periodic direction, a Coulomb truncation scheme was applied. Convergence with respect to energy cutoff and the number of empty states was explicitly verified to ensure reliable quasiparticle levels and excitonic spectra.

III. ADDITIONAL COMPUTATIONAL RESULTS

Figure S1: Top and side views of atomic structures for the 2L-MoS₂/MoSe₂ heterostructure in seven high-symmetry stacking configurations. Panels (a)–(g) correspond to the AAA, AAB, ABB, BBA, BAA, BAB, and ABA stackings, respectively, each with a unique interlayer atomic registry. These variations in stacking order affect the interlayer coupling and consequently the excitonic behavior of the heterostructure.

Figure S2: Band alignment of the 2L-MoS₂/MoSe₂ heterostructure in (a) ABA and (b) BAA stacking configurations. The system consists of two monolayers of MoS₂ (L1 and L2) and a monolayer of MoSe₂ (L3). Both stackings exhibit type-II band alignment, with the conduction band minimum (CBM) located on MoS₂ and the valence band maximum (VBM) on MoSe₂. In the ABA configuration, the band gap (E_g) of the heterostructure is defined by the CBM of L2 MoS₂ and the VBM of L3 MoSe₂, while in the BAA configuration, E_g is defined by the CBM of L1 MoS₂ and the VBM of L3 MoSe₂. The individual band gaps of L1 (E_{g1}), L2 (E_{g2}), and L3 (E_{g3}) are also indicated.

Figure S3: Partially self-consistent quasiparticle (EVGW₀@PBE) and hybrid functional (HSE06) band structures of the 2L-MoS₂/MoSe₂ heterostructure for the ABA and BAA stacking motifs. Panels (a) and (b) display EVGW₀@PBE band structures for the ABA and BAA configurations, respectively, alongside the corresponding PBE bands to illustrate the renormalization of the valence and conduction band edges. Panels (c) and (d) present HSE06 band structures for the same stackings, confirming the preservation of the qualitative layer-resolved type-II band alignment. The comparisons highlight the impact of many-body screening and validate the stacking-dependent band-edge assignments discussed in the main text.

Table S1: Calculated PL peak positions and first bright exciton energies with oscillator strengths (in parentheses) for all stacking configurations of the 2L-MoS₂/MoSe₂ heterostructure.

Stacking	PL Energy (eV)	First Bright Exciton (eV)
AAA	1.362 (0.024)	1.925 (13.23)
AAB	1.398 (0.003)	1.893 (13.41)
ABB	1.391 (0.002)	1.897 (13.38)
BBA	1.278 (0.069)	1.887 (13.43)
BAA	1.356 (0.029)	1.909 (13.68)
BAB	1.395 (0.002)	1.894 (13.43)
ABA	1.287 (0.068)	1.905 (13.79)

Figure S4: (a) Optical image of an hBN-encapsulated 2L MoS₂/MoSe₂ heterostructure on a SiO₂ substrate. The red rectangle denotes the region of the PL intensity of the ILX map shown in (b). The green square in (b) marks the PL peak energy map of the ILX in (c). In (d) two exemplary spectra from the map of (c) are shown. The energy difference of the ILX between the domains approximates to 40 meV. (e) Optical image of an hBN-encapsulated 2L-3R-MoS₂/1L-MoSe₂ heterostructure with no angular alignment on a SiO₂ substrate. (f) Exemplary PL spectra of the heterostructure in (e). Notably, no ILX peak in the low energy range can be observed, while the MoSe₂ intralayer exciton signal is quenched.

IV. OBSERVATION OF DOMAIN DEPENDENT ILX PL AND DOMAIN WALL MOTION IN AN ADDITIONAL SAMPLE

In Fig.S4a another hBN-encapsulated 2L MoS₂/MoSe₂ heterostructure is shown. It has the same stacking configuration as the one shown in Fig. 2 of the main text. Again, an ILX resonance can be seen in the whole heterostructure. The ILX shows also an energy shift of about 40 meV in the ILX energy depending on the location of the sample, while the other features shift only minimally (see fig. S4d). The different energies correspond to the different ferroelectric domains in the 3R-MoS₂ bilayer. In Fig. S5 the schematic of the device structure of the gated PL measurements as well as additional gated PL maps of the ILX energy of a hBN-encapsulated 2L MoS₂/MoSe₂ heterostructure is shown. Notably, in S5b-d, the ILX energy change by gating corresponds roughly with the energy change of the specific domain sites without gate.

Figure S5: (a) Schematic of the device structure of the gated PL measurements. (b)-(d) Gated PL maps of a 2L-3R-MoS₂/MoSe₂ sample. The white bar in (d) corresponds to 5 μm.

Figure S6: (a) AFM scan on sample from Fig.2. The green line denotes the profile shown in (b). The step height fitted approximates to 1.4 nm. (c) Optical image of the sample with the red indicator showing the size of the AFM scan (a). The white lines corresponds to roughly 5μm.

V. AFM MEASUREMENTS

In S6 the AFM topography of the sample analyzed in Fig. 2 is shown. The green line in Fig S6a and S6b depicts the profile line of the 2L MoS₂ compared from the MoSe₂ monolayer to the MoS₂/MoSe₂ heterostructure. The fit estimates roughly to 1.4 nm, corroborating the bilayer thickness of the MoS₂.

VI. REDSHIFT OF THE ILX IN DIFFERENT HETEROSTRUCTURES

Table S2: Energies of different 3R-MoS₂/MoSe₂ heterostructures with varying MoS₂ layer counts.

Heterostructure	E_{exp}^{ILX} (eV)	E_{theory}^{ILX} (eV)
1L-MoS ₂ /MoSe ₂	1.42	1.44
2L-MoS ₂ /MoSe ₂	1.34	1.36
3L-MoS ₂ /MoSe ₂	1.24	–
4L-MoS ₂ /MoSe ₂	1.16	–

Figure S7: Exemplary spectrum from a 1L-MoS₂/MoSe₂ heterostructure at 4 K.

Figure S8: SHG intensity of the sample from Fig. 2.

VII. SECOND HARMONIC GENERATION

In S8 the SHG intensity of the sample analyzed in Fig. 2 is shown. The SHG confirms the good alignment between MoS₂ and MoSe₂ with $\Delta\theta \approx 0.1^\circ$. Also by comparison of the SHG intensity of the individual layers and the heterostructure, a R-stacking can be deduced.

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- [1] P. J. Zomer, M. H. D. Guimarães, J. C. Brant, N. Tombros, and B. J. van Wees, *Applied Physics Letters* **105**, 013101 (2014).
 - [2] F. Pizzocchero, L. Gammelgaard, B. S. Jessen, J. M. Caridad, L. Wang, J. Hone, P. Bøggild, and T. J. Booth, *Nature Communications* **7**, 11894 (2016).
 - [3] P. E. Blöchl, *Physical Review B* **50**, 17953 (1994).
 - [4] G. Kresse and D. Joubert, *Physical Review B* **59**, 1758 (1999).
 - [5] G. Kresse and J. Furthmüller, *Physical Review B* **54**, 11169 (1996).
 - [6] G. Kresse and J. Furthmüller, *Computational Materials Science* **6**, 15 (1996).
 - [7] J. P. Perdew, K. Burke, and M. Ernzerhof, *Physical Review Letters* **77**, 3865 (1996).
 - [8] S. Grimme, J. Antony, S. Ehrlich, and H. Krieg, *The Journal of Chemical Physics* **132**, 154104 (2010).
 - [9] R. D. King-Smith and D. Vanderbilt, *Physical Review B* **47**, 1651 (1993).
 - [10] R. Resta, *Reviews of Modern Physics* **66**, 899 (1994).

- [11] D. Xiao, M.-C. Chang, and Q. Niu, *Reviews of Modern Physics* **82**, 1959 (2010).
- [12] M. S. Hybertsen and S. G. Louie, **34**, 5390.
- [13] W. Hanke and L. J. Sham, *Physical Review B* **21**, 4656 (1980).
- [14] G. Strinati, *Rivista del Nuovo Cimento* **11**, 1 (1988).
- [15] E. Clementi, D. L. Raimondi, and W. P. Reinhardt, *The Journal of Chemical Physics* **47**, 1300 (1967).
- [16] L. Hedin, *Phys. Rev.* **139**, A796 (1965).
- [17] M. S. Hybertsen and S. G. Louie, *Physical Review Letters* **55**, 1418 (1985).